

A pilot study of the attitudes and awareness of homœopathy shown by patients in three Manchester pharmacies

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Abstract

This pilot study was designed to determine public awareness of, and attitudes to, homœopathy by distributing a questionnaire to a random sample of patients attending three pharmacies in different areas of Greater Manchester.

It was found that 78% of the people had some degree of knowledge of homœopathy, but a significant number of these were adjudged as being from social classes A, B and C₁. Attitudes did not appear to differ between those who had used homœopathy and those who had not, there being a positive view in general.

A need for a continuing homœopathic education programme for prescribers and the provision of more information for potential patients was identified.

KEY WORDS: Homœopathy; Over the counter; Retail pharmacy; Questionnaire; Public awareness; Social class.

Introduction

Interest in homœopathy, acupuncture and herbalism is growing in the UK as the public becomes more aware of its benefits. There is also growing scepticism about the effectiveness of conventional medicine.¹ Studies have shown that most patients are turning to these unorthodox methods of health care after conventional methods have failed,²⁻⁴ although other reasons have been suggested.⁵ People are becoming more and more health conscious and aware of the effects that tobacco, alcohol and conventional drugs have on their bodies. Increased coverage of non conventional forms of medical care, including homœopathy, in the press, on television and on local radio has also contributed to an increased demand for complementary medicine. It has been shown that it is generally people in social classes ABC₁ that exhibit the greatest interest in complementary medicine.^{2,6,7}

This pilot study focused on homœopathy, the aim being to determine the extent of public knowledge, attitudes towards homœopathy, and whether social class had any significant effect. Ideas on the relative benefits of acute and

chronic homœopathic treatment were also investigated. These latter perceptions are important, for most over-the-counter treatment in pharmacies is directed towards acute prescribing.

Method

Eighty-four customers in three pharmacies were surveyed: Pharmacy A was situated near the University of Manchester, serving students and staff, pharmacy B was situated in a middle class residential area, and pharmacy C was situated in a working class area, serving mainly senior citizens and young families. Using ACORN data,⁸ the first two pharmacies were adjudged to serve people falling into social groups ABC₁ and the third into groups C₂DE.

It is acknowledged that sampling would need to be better controlled in a full study, using criteria to type respondents individually, rather than relying on the locality of the pharmacy.

While patients were waiting for prescriptions to be dispensed, some were chosen at random and invited to complete the questionnaire illustrated in Figure 1. Help was available if there was any difficulty in filling in the form. The first

1. Have you heard of homeopathy?
- | | |
|-----|----|
| Yes | No |
|-----|----|
- If you have not, please do not continue with this survey.
2. How did you hear of homeopathy?
3. Have you ever been prescribed a homeopathic remedy by your GP?
- | | |
|-----|----|
| Yes | No |
|-----|----|
4. Has a pharmacist ever recommended a remedy?
- | | |
|-----|----|
| Yes | No |
|-----|----|
5. What were your reasons for trying homeopathy ... (tick)
- conventional medicine failed ...
 - the lack of side effects ...
 - personal recommendation ...
 - other reason ... (state)
6. If you have NOT tried homeopathy, what might persuade you to try it? (tick)
- if conventional medicine failed ...
 - the lack of side effects ...
 - personal recommendation ...
 - other reason ... (state)
7. Tick any of the following remedies that are familiar to you, and state the main use if you know it
- | | |
|------------------|------------------|
| Arnica | Chamomilla |
| Arsen Alb | Gelsemium |
| Belladonna | Rhus Tox |
| Bryonia | |
8. For which conditions do you think homeopathy could be used? (tick)
- | | | | |
|-------------|--------------------|---------------------|------------------|
| Acne ... | Anxiety ... | Coughs ... | Hypertension ... |
| Allergy ... | Colds ... | Cuts, abrasions ... | Shingles ... |
| Angina ... | Colic (infant) ... | Headaches ... | Teething ... |
9. Would you administer homeopathic remedies to pets?
- | | |
|-----|----|
| Yes | No |
|-----|----|
10. In the treatment of acute conditions, do you think that homeopathic remedies are: (tick)
- Not effective ...
 - More effective than orthodox medicine ...
 - Less effective than orthodox medicine ...
 - Don't know ...
11. In the treatment of chronic (long-standing) conditions do you think that homeopathic remedies are: (tick)
- Not effective ...
 - More effective than orthodox medicine ...
 - Less effective than orthodox medicine ...
 - Don't know ...

Thank-you for taking part in this survey.

Figure 1: Questionnaire: homeopathy—public awareness and attitudes

part of the questionnaire sought to determine how people had heard about homeopathy. A second section was included to determine whether some common homeopathic medicines could be identified, together with their uses, while the final part of the questionnaire tested patients' attitudes towards homeopathy. The questionnaires of people who had not heard of

TABLE 1. Question 1—Respondents who had heard about homeopathy

Pharmacy	Number of questionnaires distributed	Number of people heard about homeopathy	%
A	39	33	85
B	35	29	83
C	10	2	20

homeopathy were excluded after Table 1 had been constructed.

Results

Eighty-four questionnaires were distributed, 39 from pharmacy A, 35 from pharmacy B, and 10 from C. Nobody refused to accept a questionnaire, but not all the questions were answered on every form, and this accounts for the different sample sizes in the results.

TABLE 2. Homeopathic knowledge and social class (by pharmacy used)

Group	Social class		
	ABC1	C2DE	N
People with some homeopathic knowledge	62	2	64
People with no homeopathic knowledge	12	8	20
Totals	74	10	84

Chi squared value = 23.2 (df = 1)

Significant at 5% level

Questions 1–4—exposure to homeopathy

Table 1 shows that 33 (85%) of the people who were given forms in pharmacy A had heard

TABLE 3. Question 2—Source of information on homeopathy (n = 52)

Main source of information on homeopathy	Number of respondents	%
Neighbours/friends	7	13
Relatives	5	9
Pharmacist	13	23
Media	17	31
Leaflets	2	4
Trying product	1	2
Educational source	2	4
GP	4	7
Nursing staff	1	2

TABLE 4. Questions 5 & 6—Respondents' reasons for using or considering homœopathy, and the method of scoring their answers

Answer	Number consider because . . .	Number have used because . . .	Remarks on scoring system	Score per answer
conventional medicine ineffective	14 (47%)	11 (42%)	Negative approach—homœopathy as last resort	1
lack of side effects	6 (20%)	13 (50%)	A more positive approach to homœopathy	2
on recommendation	18 (60%)	17 (65%)	Trying homœopathy on its merits	3
Unlikely to use	1 (3%)	0	A negative approach	-1
Sample size	30	26		

about homœopathy, 29 (83%) in pharmacy B, but only 2 (20%) in pharmacy C. The results were analysed in terms of social groupings and are displayed in Table 2. A chi-squared test was carried out and Yates continuity correction applied. The results were significant at the 5% level, demonstrating a correlation between social class and awareness of homœopathic treatment.

Of the 55 respondents who answered positively to question 1, 17 (31%) said they had heard about homœopathy through the media, and 13 (23%) from their local pharmacist; in fact the pharmacist in Pharmacy B actively promoted homœopathy and indeed appeared in a radio programme on the subject each month. More people had become aware of homœopathy collectively through relatives or friends (22%) than through their GP (7%). See Table 3.

A homœopathic medicine had been recommended by a GP in 10 cases (16%) and by a pharmacist in 17 cases (27%).

Questions 5 and 6—Reasons for using, or considering the use of, homœopathic medicines
Several responders gave more than one reason for using or considering the use of homœopathy; this accounts for the discrepancy between the total sample size and the total number of

responses. A scoring system was devised for the answers to questions 5 and 6 (See Table 4), and a significance test carried out to ascertain if there was any difference in attitudes between people who had already tried homœopathic medicines and those who had not yet taken the 'plunge'. The results were not significant and no difference in attitude could therefore be detected between the two groups.

Question 7—Ability to identify names and uses of homœopathic medicine

Of all the homœopathic medicines listed on the questionnaire, *Arnica* was the most frequently identified, with 21 respondents (33%) recognizing the name, and 15 (23%) identifying its use correctly. *Belladonna* was recognized by 15 people (24%), and *Chamomilla* by 14 people (22%). The top six medicines are listed in Table 6.

Question 8—Uses of medicines

Question 8 was answered by 63 respondents. 18% of the sample stated that homœopathy could play a role in all the conditions listed. The

TABLE 5. Significance test on results to Question 5 and 6

Group	N	Score	Mean	SD
Would consider homœopathy for reasons given in Table 4	30	79	2.63	1.40
Tried homœopathy for reasons given in Table 4	26	88	3.38	1.55

$z = 0.95$: not significant at 5% level

TABLE 6. Question 7—Respondents' identification of names and uses of common remedies

Name of homœopathic medicine	Number of respondents identifying name of medicine	Number of respondents identifying use of medicine
<i>Arnica</i>	21 (33%)	15 (23%)
<i>Arsen. alb.</i>	4 (8%)	3 (5%)
<i>Belladonna</i>	15 (24%)	8 (13%)
<i>Bryonia</i>	3 (5%)	1 (2%)
<i>Chamomilla</i>	14 (22%)	7 (11%)
<i>Rhus tox.</i>	7 (11%)	4 (6%)

TABLE 7. Question 8—Identifying the applications of homœopathy

Condition	Number of responses	% total responses
Acne	25	40
Allergies	39	61
Angina	20	32
Anxiety	49	77
Colds	49	76
Colic—infants	19	29
Coughs	34	53
Cuts & Abrasions	22	34
Headaches	38	60
Hypertension	23	35
Shingles	17	27
Teething	22	34

majority (77%) associated homœopathy with anxiety or stress and (76%) with the treatment of colds and catarrh. Fewer people 17 (27%) recognized homœopathy as a treatment for shingles. The results are presented in Table 7.

Question 9—Use of homœopathy in pet care

Twenty-three people (49%) said they would give homœopathic medicines to their pets.

Questions 10 and 11—Homœopathy in acute and chronic disease

The results to questions 11 and 12 are summarized in Figure 2. The most favoured perception

of the sample was that homœopathy is equally effective as conventional medicines in the treatment of acute illness but somewhat less successful in the treatment of chronic conditions.

Discussion

The study shows that a high percentage of people in the sample had some knowledge of homœopathic medicine. This knowledge appeared to be confined almost exclusively to people with a higher level of education, and in higher social classes. This may be due to the fact that homœopathy is often practised outside the National Health Service and in these circumstances, the full cost of treatment has to be borne by the patient. People in higher social classes and with a tertiary level of education are more likely to have a higher disposable income. However, homœopathy is available on the National Health Service, and it has been shown that general practitioners and medical students may react favourably to complementary medicine,⁹ so there should be no reason for this apparent class difference. Our findings suggest that some patients are prevented from taking advantage of homœopathy due to lack of promotion by health care professionals, rather than from a lack of funds. Indeed more people had heard of homœopathy from friends or relatives than from their GPs.

Previous studies have found that there is no significant difference in attitude between people who had tried homœopathy and those who had

Figure 2: Effectiveness of homœopathic medicines with respect to allopathic treatments

not,^{4,10} and a similar result was found here. It is not surprising that *Arnica* was the medicine most frequently identified, as it is a polychrest with a wide range of applications and presentations. It is used topically in first aid for the treatment of bruising and local injuries, especially in sport.

It is interesting that so many people identified anxiety and stress as responding to homoeopathic treatment. This awareness could be due to media attention on the dependence properties of conventional anti-depressants. Colds and hayfever were also identified as possible targets for homoeopathy, and this is possibly due to a dissatisfaction with the side effects and efficacy of existing treatments.

Homoeopathic medicines have an increasing part to play in treatment of companion animals, and the large number of positive answers to question 9 reflects this. *Arnica* also features strongly in veterinary prescribing.¹¹

The fact that a higher number of people thought homoeopathy had a greater role to play in treating acute conditions than it did in chronic conditions is important to pharmacists, because most of their counter prescribing is directed towards the former.

It appears that few respondents thought homoeopathy to be more successful than conventional medicine.

The results demonstrate an urgent need for an

education policy directed towards both prescribers and potential patients.

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